

Special Relativity Energy-Momentum Relation in terms of Projections Part II

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In Part I of this note we considered searching for a single equation which would describe either a photon or a free particle with rest mass. We noted that these two objects have different dispersion relations, but that one could consider v/c as playing the role of a projection e.g. behaving like $\cos(\theta)$.

In this note we revisit the two dispersion relationships and see how they may become the same if $v \rightarrow c$. We then focus on the relation for light i.e. $E=pc$ and note that it is the function of two variables E and p . We suggest the single equation describing a rest mass particle and photon should also be a function of E and p , but p is proportional to E/v for a particle with rest mass. In other words v does not disappear, but it may be made to disappear if one considers projections as done in Part I. The ultimate result is a single equation in c, m_0, p and E . The variable v is completely gone explicitly. This is in keeping with special relativity which treats $(p, E), (x, t)$ and other quantities as 4-vectors, but not velocity. Thus p and E seem to be the important variables in the picture with velocity (for both light and a rest mass particle) given by dE/dp . We carry this idea of the importance of E and p further by arguing that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ holds for both light and rest mass particles and A has the same value at periodic bn/E time intervals and bn/p space intervals where b is a constant and $n=0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$. Thus there is a kind of invariance at these points regardless of velocity. We argue that this scenario is linked to the quantum mechanics of a free particle.

Newtonian Mechanics and Special Relativity

Newtonian mechanics seems to be largely based on velocity even though E (energy) and p (momentum) appear in the theory. The second law $dp/dt = F$ usually becomes a differential equation in dv/dt . Thus Newtonian mechanics seems to be focused on finding $x(t)$ which is directly linked to velocity. Special relativity on the other hand seems to be more focused on (p, E) and (x, t) . Velocity is not part of a four-vector. Furthermore for a free particle or photon, velocity may be obtained from $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ as $dE/dp = v$ if one uses $p = Ev/c^2$. In other words one may focus on p and E and consider velocity a derivative of these.

Starting with Newtonian mechanics, however, it is not so obvious that velocity should "disappear" from an E, p equation.

A Single Equation to Describe a Photon or a Free Rest Mass Particle

As in Part I we begin with the objective of finding a single equation containing E and p and possibly other parameters which describes either a photon or free particle with rest mass. These two objects seem to be very different as they have different dispersion relations as noted in Part I:

$$p = E/b v \quad (b = \text{constant}) \quad \text{particle with rest mass} \quad ((1a)) \quad E = pc \quad (\text{photon}) \quad ((1b))$$

At this point we ask whether one may arrange for ((1a)) and ((1b)) to be essentially the same, something not done in Part I. If b is chosen to be cc then ((1a)) and ((1b)) become the same in the limit $v \rightarrow c$. Furthermore v/c in the form of a ratio which is like a projection e.g. $\cos(\theta)$. This idea used in Part I needs to be strengthened. It is not only a free particle with rest mass which may be associated with a velocity v , but also a photon as shown by Einstein in 1905 (1). Consider a photon moving up hitting a wall and bouncing back in a frame moving at velocity v with respect to the lab. From the point of view of the person in the lab, the photon moves in such a way as to make a right angle triangle as it moves up. The speed on the hypotenuse is c and that along the motion direction is v . Thus $p' \cos(\theta) = p' v/c$, but for a photon $p'c = E'$ so the component of p along the motion direction is $E'v/cc$. This suggests one may use v/c as $\cos(\theta)$. To make this more direct, one may consider a photon bouncing up and down perpendicular to the motion of the box as rest mass that now has momentum. The momentum as argued is $p'v/c$, but there is also a $p'\sin(\theta)$ term. If $v \rightarrow 0$, the $p'\sin(\theta)$ term must yield the original energy of the photon simply moving up and down. I.e. E without ($'$). This is the same argument that we applied for a particle in Part I i.e. one has:

$$E'E' = E'E' v/c v/c + E'E' (1-vv/cc) \quad ((2a))$$

The second term on the RHS side should be proportional to E so E' should behave as $E/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ in other words the second term in ((2a)) is EE or proportional to rest mass squared where rest mass E is the energy of the photon moving up and down with no v motion. The fact that a photon may act as a particle with rest mass strengthens the idea that one equation should describe both a photon and a free particle with rest mass.

For a particle with rest mass:

$$EE = EE \cos(\theta)\cos(\theta) + EE \sin(\theta) \sin(\theta) \quad ((2b))$$

$$EE = EE v/c v/c + EE (1-vv/cc) \quad ((3))$$

The second term on the RHS side disappears for light and so one may consider it proportional to m_0 (as light has $m_0=0$). If the second term is to remain for $v \rightarrow c$ then $E=ccm_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ is a solution.

Thus one is able to remove “ v ” explicitly from the problem (although implicitly it exists for the particle with rest mass) i.e. one has:

$$EE = ppcc + momo cccc \quad ((4))$$

This is strictly a function of E , p and two parameters m_0 and c (at least in a vacuum). It may be noted that the photon dispersion relationship is also only a function of E and p because v is a constant. The interesting feature of ((4)) is that one is able to describe both objects (free rest

mass particle and photon) in terms of only two variables. One is able to explicitly remove the v variable which appears in the free rest mass particle's dispersion relationship using the projection approach. Furthermore one may find velocity for either the case of a photon or free particle with rest mass in the same way:

$dE/dp = pcc/E = (E/cc) vcc/E = v$ for a particle with rest mass and:

$dE/dp = pcc/E = Ec/E$ for a photon ((5))

Thus an E, p description seems to work for both a free particle with rest mass and a photon with explicit velocity as a variable (for the free rest mass particle) disappearing. Velocity may be obtained by taking a derivative using only E and p i.e. dE/dp . This seems to be a special relativistic scenario of the situation which seems to differ from the viewpoint of Newtonian mechanics which is velocity centric. A question arises, however: May one obtain further information by considering E and p ?

E and P and the Idea of Wavelength and Frequency

In the above scenario we argued that one may take the two different dispersion relationships, one explicit in v (particle with rest mass), and obtain a general equation in E, p, m_0 and c with no explicit v . This equation holds both for a free particle with rest mass and a photon and is in keeping with the special relativistic view of p, E as a 4-vector. Velocity in a sense is not central and may be obtained from dE/dp .

If one chooses this special relativistic viewpoint, one may wonder whether any further physics may be surmised. It is known that:

$A = -Et + px$ ((6)) is a Lorentz invariant.

This invariant has the same value for periodic intervals in time i.e. nb/E and space nb/p where n is $0, 1, 2, \dots$ and b a constant. If the notion of a Lorentz invariant is to have importance it seems one should consider this a relevant result. Velocity is no longer the central focus, but a particle still moves with a velocity. Nevertheless, given an E and p , time and space seem to be broken into units proportional to $1/E$ and $1/p$, both for a photon and free particle with rest mass as the same relativistic formalism applies to both. In other words there is a frequency and wavelength for both a photon and a free particle with rest mass. We argue that this follows from taking an E, p -centric view which is the basis of special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a free particle with rest mass dispersion relationship and that of a photon may be made to look the same for $v \rightarrow c$ if E/cc is used in place of m_0 in $p = mv$ i.e. $p = Ev/cc$. In such a case, one may create an equation which eliminates v explicitly as done in Part I, by considering v/c a projection such as $\cos(\theta)$. This leads to $EE = EE \cos(\theta)\cos(\theta) + EE \sin(\theta)\sin(\theta)$ with the later term becoming $m_0 m_0 c^2 c^2$ as

shown in Part I. In other words one is left with an equation $E^2 = pc^2 + m^2c^4$ which is a function of the variables p, E which are part of a special relativistic 4-vector. Velocity is not part of a 4-vector and disappears leaving an equation which describes both a photon and free rest mass particle. We also conclude that one may extend the importance of p and E in this special relativistic scenario by considering the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which has the same value at periodic time intervals bn/E and space intervals bn/p where b is a constant and n an integer. Thus space and time are broken into divisions regardless of velocity (which is dE/dp). We argue that this is the basis of frequency and wavelength for both a photon and free rest mass particle. This is not to say that velocity is not present, rather p and E and their special relativistic relationships seem to be central and lead to new physics in the sense of a wavelength and frequency which are not apparent in Newtonian mechanics.

References

1. Einstein's Original 1905 Papers
<https://guides.loc.gov/einstein-annus-mirabilis/1905-papers>